

SDC-1

SAMPLE DESCRIPTION

Table SDC-1-1. Sample of transplant coordinator teams

Autonomous Community	Hospital	Number of ICOD donations in 2018 (per hospital)	Number of ICOD donations in 2018 (per stratum)	Number of total ICOD donations in 2018 (per autonomous community)
Andalusia	Hospital Universitario Virgen de la Macarena	14	35	102
	Hospital Universitario Reina Sofía	11		
	Hospital Regional Universitario de Málaga	10		
Aragon	Hospital Universitario Miguel Servet	18	18	23
Asturias	Hospital Universitario Central de Asturias	24	24	24
Balearic Islands	Hospital Universitario Son Espases	26	26	26
Canary Islands	Hospital de Gran Canarias Dr. Negrin	10	15	47
	Hospital Universitario Insular de Gran Canaria	5		
Cantabria	Hospital Universitario Marqués de Valdecilla	6	6	6
Castile-La Mancha	Hospital Universitario Virgen de la Salud	6	6	34
Castile-León	Complejo Asistencial de Burgos	10	10	27
Catalonia	Hospital Universitario Vall D Hebron	24	52	92
	Hospital Universitario de Gerona Dr Josep Trueta	28		
Extremadura	Hospital Infanta Cristina	22	22	22
Galicia	Complejo Hospitalario Universitario de Santiago de Compostela	32	32	44
La Rioja	Hospital San Pedro	12	12	12
Madrid	Hospital Universitario Gregorio Marañón	24	52	60
	Hospital Universitario Ramon y Cajal	18		
	Hospital Universitario de la Princesa	10		
Murcia	Hospital Universitario Virgen de la Arrixaca	13	13	13
Navarre	Hospital Universitario de Navarra	26	26	26
Basque Country	Hospital Universitario de Araba	14	14	31
Valencia	Hospital Universitario Dr Balmis	8	8	29
	TOTAL (23 hospitals)	371	371	618

Note: ICOD, intensive care to facilitate organ donation.

SDC-2

INTERVIEW SCRIPT

Screening and identification of the potential donor.

How is potential donor screening done?

When and how do I receive the notice?

Who and from what units is it done?

Who receives it?

What difficulties may exist in determining which patients are candidates for controlled ICOD?

What is the approximate percentage of cases that are difficult to identify?

Preparing of the Early Interview

How do you personally prepare for the interview with family members?

What goals do you set for yourself before starting the interview?

How do you make the decision of which family members to include in the interview?

What strategies do you use to select family members for the interview?

Is there any coordination with the health personnel who treated the potential donor? If yes, can you describe it/s?

Do you explore the information that family members have about their family member's health status?

If yes: How do you do it?

How do you prepare yourself emotionally for the interview?

Any other technical or personal steps you take before starting the interview?

Early interview with family members (I). Start of the interview.

How do you start the interview with the family?

Verbal behavior: What do you say at the beginning of the interview?

Nonverbal Communication: How Do You Say It?

Interpersonal distance.

Emphasis on language, eye contact.

Emotional expressions you're trying to convey.

Development of the early interview with family members (II). During the interview. Emotional reactions

How do you deal with the family's emotional reactions?

What are the most frequent emotional reactions of the interviewees?

How do you approach them?

What are the most difficult emotional reactions?

How do you approach them?

Development of early interviews with family members (III). During the interview. Strategies for applying for ICOD permission.

What strategies do you use in the ICOD consent request?

What arguments are used to support the petition?

What metaphors do you use to exemplify the process and support the petition?

How is the question of the will of the deceased handled?

How do you inquire about the expression or registration of your will?

How do you deal with the different situations in which there is some evidence (registration of last wills, verbal expression...)

How do you handle situations when there is no such evidence?

Development of the early interview with family members (IV). Family Reactions and Strategies for Obtaining Permission

What characteristics or reactions of the family are associated with the granting of permission?

Describe all the positive reactions.

What are the first "clues" or signs that make you think the family will accept?

How do you modulate your performance based on this initial feedback?

What family characteristics or reactions are associated with the denial of permission?

Describe all the negative reactions.

What are the first "clues" or signs that the family is going to deny permission?

How do you modulate your performance based on this initial feedback?

What are the main reasons families give for denying permission for ICOD?

Cite all the reasons given for denying permission

What are the main strategies and arguments you follow in the face of doubts or denial of consent by the family?

Which of these strategies and arguments are most effective in getting families to change perspective and accept?

If not, how long do you insist?

In the case of consent, what agreements do you reach with the family about the evolution of the family member?

Cite the agreements

How long is the waiting time agreed with the family until the evolution to brain death?

How do family dynamics influence obtaining permission?

What are the family dynamics that, during the interview, are perceived as most favorable for obtaining permission?

What are the family dynamics that, during the interview, are perceived as most detrimental to obtaining permission?

How do you handle communication with several different people and opinions?

How do you act in cases where there is a situation of conflict/confrontation between several family members on the issue of consent?

Post-Early Interview actions

How do you feel after the interview?

What positive and negative feelings do you have?

What does those feelings depend on?

Is there a message that you give yourself on a regular basis that helps you approach the post-interview?

Do you value the fulfillment of the goals you were taking?

What do you do when the patient does not progress to brain death in the time agreed with the relatives?

Cite all the measures that could be taken.

On what does its effectiveness depend for the final obtaining of the permit?

From the Early Interview to permission for donation.

What happens between obtaining consent at the pre-interview and obtaining consent for donation?

Indicate all relevant events.

What factors or conditions can alter this process?

Results of the center's activity

What is the approximate percentage of consent for the implementation of ICODs obtained at the center?

SDC-3

Detailed description of analysis and quality control

The texts of the interviews were analyzed using content analysis^{1,2}, which is a research technique for making replicable and valid inferences from texts. Content analysis was applied to reduce the textual information by codification into structured topics (first-level of codification) and categories (second level of codification).

The first codification was conducted using a preconfigured topic structure derived from the interview script and included the main areas explored in the interviews. The second level of coding was generated inductively by analyzing specific answers. Coding was conducted, verified, and reformulated by three members of the research team through an inter-rater consensus system using a Delphi panel procedure. This was selected to generate a highly specific code system with a low level of inference, whereby the code tags were close to the literalness of the response. This system offers a lower condensation of information and direct presentation of the results through a descriptive frequency analysis, reducing the level of subjectivity. The number of categories for answers to open questions vary depending on the extent of answers obtained. This system prioritizes obtaining a broad overview over assessing the frequency of each category.

The final coding was subjected to quality control by another member of the research team, who performed independent coding of a random selection of nodes. Mean inter-rater reliability (kappa index of 0.81/1) was 0.73–1.00, indicating good or very good reliability, particularly considering the exploratory-

descriptive character of the present study^{3,4}. N-Vivo® V.12 (QSR-International-Lumivero, Denver, CO, USA) was used for qualitative analysis.

The sample achieved an adequate representation of population data based on (1) the sample size relative to total population size (23/51 Spanish TCTs participating in ICOD procedures; TCTs responsible for 371/618 ICOD donations registered in Spain in 2018); (2) high specificity of the subject of study; (3) sample diversity regarding participant characteristics, number of yearly ICOD donations, and geographical origin; and (4) level of redundancy regarding central topics of the retrieved information regarding TCTs' experiences and perceptions.

An initial report of the methodology and results was sent to the 23 participating TCTs and two experts from the National Transplant Organization for review and suggestions for possible modifications. Suggestions were received from two TCTs; additionally, various terminological suggestions from the National Transplant Organization experts were incorporated into the final version. This study followed the consolidated criteria for reporting qualitative research (COREQ)⁵. The checklist of fulfillment of the 32 COREQ criteria is included in the Supplemental Digital Content.

REFERENCES

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SDC-4

Consolidated criteria for reporting qualitative studies (COREQ): 32-item checklist

No	Item	Guide questions/description	Manuscript Check
Domain 1: Research team and reflexivity			
Personal Characteristics			
1.	Interviewer/facilitator	Which author/s conducted the interview or focus group?	It has been described in a generic way in Methods' section ((Section 2.6.) to preserve blind peer review. It will be included in the final manuscript.
2.	Credentials	What were the researcher's credentials? <i>E.g. PhD, MD</i>	As described in Methods' section (Section 2.6.) interviewers were 5 doctors in psychology
3.	Occupation	What was their occupation at the time of the study?	As described in Methods' section (Section 2.6.), interviewers were university professors with no connection to the transplant system.
4.	Gender	Was the researcher male or female?	As been described in Methods' section (Section 2.6.), interviewers were one woman and four men.
5.	Experience and training	What experience or training did the researcher have?	As described in Methods' section (Section 2.6.), interviewers were senior researchers. They account an average of 15 years of experience in qualitative research.
Relationship with participants			
6.	Relationship established	Was a relationship established prior to study commencement?	As described in Methods' section (Section 2.6.), no prior relationship was established with participants.
7.	Participant knowledge of the interviewer	What did the participants know about the researcher? <i>e.g. personal goals, reasons for doing the research</i>	As described in Methods' section (Section 2.6.), participants were provided with an information sheet detailing study and researchers' goal and objectives
8.	Interviewer characteristics	What characteristics were reported about the interviewer/facilitator? <i>e.g. Bias, assumptions, reasons and interests in the research topic</i>	As described in Methods' section (Section 2.6.), participants were provided with an information sheet detailing study and researchers' reasons and interests.ñ
Domain 2: study design			
Theoretical framework			
9.	Methodological orientation and Theory	What methodological orientation was stated to underpin the study? <i>e.g. grounded theory, discourse analysis, ethnography, phenomenology, content analysis</i>	As described in Methods' section (section 2.7.), Content Analysis (Krippendorff, 2004) was used as methodological orientation
Participant selection			
10.	Sampling	How were participants selected? <i>e.g. purposive, convenience, consecutive, snowball</i>	As described in Methods' section (section 2.4), the study used a stratified random sample of 23 Transplant Coordination Teams from the total 51 teams involved in ICOD procedures in 2018 in Spain
11.	Method of approach	How were participants approached? <i>e.g. face-to-face, telephone, mail, email</i>	As been described in Methods' section (section 2.6.), participants were located through the mediation of Spanish National Transplant Organization staff, who anticipated the objectives

			of the study and enquired for their availability. Subsequently, a member of the researchers linked to the university centers made telephonic or e-mail contact and arranged the moment of the interview.
12.	Sample size	How many participants were in the study?	As described in Methods' section (section 2.4.) interviewees comprised 17 men and 17 women; 28 were intensive care doctors, and six were intensive care nurses..
13.	Non-participation	How many people refused to participate or dropped out? Reasons?	As described in Methods' section (section 2.4.), all the initially selected teams agreed to participate in the interviews
Setting			
14.	Setting of data collection	Where was the data collected? e.g. <i>home, clinic, workplace</i>	As described in Methods' section (section 2.6.), f the 23 interviews conducted, 16 were carried out in person at the hospital center of the TCT, six were carried out virtually using Zoom® and Skype® tools because of the overlap with the COVID-19 pandemic period, and one in a mixed interview (face-to-face and virtual).
15.	Presence of non-participants	Was anyone else present besides the participants and researchers?	As described in Methods' section (section 2.6), No one else was present besides the participants and researchers
16.	Description of sample	What are the important characteristics of the sample? e.g. <i>demographic data, date</i>	As described in Methods' section (section 2.6.), interviewees comprised 17 men and 17 women; 28 were intensive care doctors, and six were intensive care nurses and fieldwork was conducted from July 2019 to September 2021.
Data collection			
17.	Interview guide	Were questions, prompts, guides provided by the authors? Was it pilot tested?	Interview Script is included as Supplementary Material-1. Interview script was piloted with an initial sample of three interviews and reviewed.
18.	Repeat interviews	Were repeat interviews carried out? If yes, how many?	As described in Methods' section (section 2.6.), no repeat interviews were carried out..
19.	Audio/visual recording	Did the research use audio or visual recording to collect the data?	As described in Methods' section (section 2.6.), audio recording was used to collect data.
20.	Field notes	Were field notes made during and/or after the interview or focus group?	As described in Methods' section (section 2.6.), interviewers filled out a brief field report to register participants' characteristics, interview climate, duration, and any other relevant aspects after completing the interview.
21.	Duration	What was the duration of the interviews or focus group?	As described in Methods' section (2.6.), the average duration of the interviews was 121 minutes, with a range of 49–226 minutes.
22.	Data saturation	Was data saturation discussed?	Though saturation is not used as criterion in Content Analysis, representativeness of data has been discussed in Methods' section (section 2.7.). The research team estimated that the sample achieved an adequate representation of populational data based on 1) sample size relative to total population size (23/51 TCTs); 2) high specificity of the subject of study; 3) sample diversity regarding participant characteristics, number of yearly ICOD donations, and geographical origin; and 4) level of redundancy regarding central topics of the retrieved information about TCTs experiences and perceptions.

23.	Transcripts returned	Were transcripts returned to participants for comment and/or correction?	As described in Methods' section (section 2.7.), members of the research team reviewed the transcripts, but the possibility of the TCTs reviewing the transcripts was ruled out, considering their workload saturation. However research report was sent to 23 participating teams and two experts from the National Transplant Organization for review and suggestions for possible modifications.
Domain 3: analysis and findings			
Data analysis			
24.	Number of data coders	How many data coders coded the data?	As described in Methods' section (section 2.7.), final coding was performed by three members of the research team and an additional member of the team performed an independent coding of a random selection of nodes for quality control.
25.	Description of the coding tree	Did authors provide a description of the coding tree?	Figure 2 describes the first level codification structure. Tables included in Results Section (section 3.) reproduce second level codification structure.
26.	Derivation of themes	Were themes identified in advance or derived from the data?	As described in Methods' section (section 2.7.), first-level coding was identified in advance and second-level of coding was derived from the data.
27.	Software	What software, if applicable, was used to manage the data?	As described in Methods' section (section 2.7.), The qualitative analysis software N-Vivo® V.12 (QSR-International-Lumivero, Denver, CO, USA) was used as support for the whole process..
28.	Participant checking	Did participants provide feedback on the findings?	As described in Methods' section (section 2.7.), research report was sent to 23 participating teams and suggestions were received from two coordination teams
Reporting			
29.	Quotations presented	Were participant quotations presented to illustrate the themes / findings? Was each quotation identified? e.g. <i>participant number</i>	Selected quotations are included as Supplementary Material-5. Quotations are identified by participant codes.
30.	Data and findings consistent	Was there consistency between the data presented and the findings?	Categories' content and frequencies are exhaustively described. On this basis, findings have been double-checked by research team members to ensure consistency between data and findings (section 3. Results).
31.	Clarity of major themes	Were major themes clearly presented in the findings?	Results descriptions is structured following major themes and the presentation of findings has been focused on them (section 3. Results).
32.	Clarity of minor themes	Is there a description of diverse cases or discussion of minor themes?	Categories yielding low frequency are also included; discussion of minor themes has been limited in this work due to space limitations (sections 3.Results and 4. Discussion) .

SDC-5

SELECTED INTERVIEW QUOTATIONS

The following interview quotations were selected and translated to illustrate how the interviewed Transplant Coordination Teams prepares and develops their approach to the family to request their consent for Intensive Care for Organ Donation. Among the different interviews, a sample of quotations with the richest and most condensed descriptions were selected.

Abbreviations:

TC: Transplant coordinator

I: Interviewer

HCX: Research Hospital Center Code

ICU: Intensive Care Unit

HC5

'**TC:** It's the same preparation as for a normal family interview of organ donation request, there is nothing special. I know that I have to inform a family about a process. We are intensivists and also transplant coordinators; you are going to inform a family about what the patients usually present, brain hemorrhages, a massive brain injury that is not addressable, either from a medical or surgical viewpoint. And you are going to inform them that there is no solution for the patient, like you always do as an intensivist doctor or as a transplant coordinator. The next step is to inform them that there is no treatment, no possibility of medical or surgical treatment and that the most likely evolution is brain death. And the family often asks you, "What will happen?" The same approach that we have for donations in general.'

HC6

'**TC:** Well, like I said, we go to a room, which has no barrier or, if there is one... if there is a table, we set it aside, we sit down in this room with the doctor who treated the patient, who tells them that their relative ... has had a cerebral hemorrhage, for example, which is the cause... the cause of this patient's coma, for example. Then, as a result of that, we address them and we... I tell them "Like my partner has informed you, your relative has a significant brain hematoma, and the only thing ...", I explain... in a clear way, I explain the consequences of such a hematoma... I make it clear that the relative will die from it, one way or another. We do not know when, maybe in 5 minutes, maybe in 3 hours. We cannot tell, the only thing we can tell them is that he will die from that. Then, I leave them alone for a while ... I always tell them if they... have any doubts, anything they want to ask me and, well, then one of them asks something and then... they start crying, and I usually wait for them to give me a chance to propose the donation. It can vary depending on each family, the time, and such... and that's when... I tell them that not everything is over; they and their family have the chance to... to go on with the... with the life of... of [other] patients because what I do is... I place them in the situation so that they are the ones in whose hands it lies because ... they can help save other people's lives. We cannot... we doctors can no longer apply any drugs, we no longer have ...

in very simply, we tell them there are no more operations we can do, there are no more drugs, that... with our means, we cannot do anything more for them. But they--the dying relative and the family-- have that chance to to help, to save other people. '

HC8

'TC: The presentation is not made directly because, at that time, the shock is sometimes very sudden... No, usually, what we do is go on giving information; we introduce ourselves. I always introduce myself with the ICU doctor, and we always leave them .. Of course, admission to the ICU has the goal of donation, right? And then, we tell them that all the measures that will be performed will ensure the patient's comfort and that the only objective is to comply with their right to decide. So they know this option exists. In principle, the interview does not aim to obtain the organs, as I said before. It is to accompany them at that moment and to offer them the possibility that exists, and inform them they have this right...

I: Okay, like the first interview, and let them think about it...

TC: That's right, because, of course, they're going to receive the... the news from the treating doctor before calling us, telling them that the patient's prognosis is fateful, and then, when they call us, it is like the second contact with the doctor ...

I: It's like the second time, to be...

TC: Of course, the first time, the doctor is the one who has told them that the prognosis is fatal... and then, when he calls us, then, it is the second interview because that is when the diagnosis is reinforced, and that is when we enter the scene, not to give all the news at once, not to tell them their relative is going to die, and they can donate, but to give them some time to assume this, because it is a previous interview, right?'

HC9

'TC: In the donation-oriented intensive care interview, you are alert to feelings and information, and then, as you receive feelings and information, you direct your interview to where you think it should go. That is what I was telling you before, wasn't it? You face a family that supposedly knows that their loved one is sick, but suddenly you realize that they have no idea; you are there, and you are telling them something that does not match what your colleagues told them, right? So you're alert to know how things are, aren't you? If we're talking about the brain death interview, come on, we're all there, at least, I'm waiting for the "What now?", huh?, because the "What now?" in brain death interviews means a lot of things. It means that the family has already assumed how things are; they have already understood that their loved one has died, and we are waiting for the "What?," and then, the "What now?" In intensive care, you are alert to know the circumstances, how the family feels, what they know, what they can do, and what you can contribute to them, right?'

HC10

I: When you have to approach that interview, what is on your mind as priorities or as objectives to be met in that interview?

TC: The first priority is that they understand there is nothing to be done for their relative. That is my first priority, so there is no doubt that something could be done but it won't be done. That is the first priority, that it is very clear that their relative-- the patient-- has no chance to survive.. um... in the following hours or days, that is my first priority. The second priority is to tell them about the benefit that the other relatives, especially the family, can... contribute to other people. '

HC14

TC: The emergency doctor, the neurologist, has to tell them that the prognosis is fatal and that he is going to die; he has to use the phrase, "He is going to die." "And when?" "We don't know." And that's it. From the psychological point of view, if they have understood, their mourning begins. If they have understood that no medical assistance can do any good, it will not heal him, he cannot go back to his previous situation like he was before, then they are already assuming this.

I: You, you as an intensivist, eh, do you always distance yourself from that communication or are there times when...?

TC: No, no, no, that communication has to be made by the emergency doctor, and we also made that clear. We made it clear in the guidelines of ICOD procedure and in another document elaborated by the ONT on recommendations for the interview. That information must be given by the doctor in charge, the person in charge is the one who clearly tells them that the patient is going to die.

I: And when do you then enter the process? Once they have communicated?

TC: When that has been said, of course! I have seen them, and I make sure that the emergency doctor has told the family that the patient is going to die, "Understood? He's going to die." "Has he told them?" "Yes." "Okay. Have you told them to go in to see him?" "No." "Let them go in and see him." Seeing him shows them that he is in a coma, whether or not he is intubated. Well, they know the prognosis is fatal, and he will die. Yes, let them go in and see him. Seeing him in a coma will impress them, whether or not he is intubated.

I: How do you go about that process; when do you decide to enter?

TC: Once the emergency doctor or neurologist has communicated that he is going to die, I enter, after they have seen the patient, and we have left them alone for a few minutes. They leave the room, and then I make contact. During this contact, I begin at the beginning, to know the family's degree of comprehension of the situation.

I: That would be your first goal?

TC: Sure! That must be the goal because I cannot assume they understood something without checking it first. You cannot start interviewing without knowing where you are, where the family is, like I said, no way. You cannot just go ahead; you must stay behind, always behind, to know where they are and then intervene, okay? They have understood that the prognosis is fatal; okay, very well. Then, you have to evaluate their capacity to make decisions because the family may be present, but perhaps some of those who have to make decisions are absent. Maybe the patient's son, who was the eldest, is the one who has to decide because the daughter is younger, or maybe the patient was estranged from his other son, and they cannot make a decision. That does not mean that you do not inform them because it is your duty, and they have the right to receive the information. Then you have to see their capacity to take control of the situation before giving them all the information. '

HC17

TC: I always try to explain first that someone has already informed them, but that I will go back in the story. Well, "You know, he was at home and this happened, and unfortunately, the hemorrhage was very massive, and the neurosurgeon has already told you that, unfortunately, he will not recover, he's going to die." "I don't know how, I don't know how when." I always try to do two or three things that I like to do, right? The first is to try to... well, to see the positive side, although there is almost none, but I try, well, I always say, he did not suffer at all, which is usual in these patients, because the bleeding was so massive that he had practically no time to realize what was happening, and he was very old, if he was old, right? I'm making up a case. Maybe I'm telling you this, and tomorrow, we receive a 15-year-old patient. But, well, I say he was already 80 years old, he did not realize what was happening, almost all of us would like that to happen to us. It would have been better if it had not happened, it would have been better. But well, if it does happen, better like this without knowing and so on; he lived a good life until this ... this... until today, this morning and such. So I always try to see something positive because he didn't suffer at all, as if nothing had happened to him. Some families wonder about this, I always try to get it out of their heads, ah... "if I had been sleeping with him instead of going out to dinner" and so on, and I say "No, with such a hemorrhage, there was nothing you could have done." I do not like them to go on thinking that if they had realized what was happening half an hour before and had called the emergency service, he would have been cured. Among other things, because I am convinced that this is not true. It also seems absurd at that time, if the patient is going to die to tell them, "Okay if you had not had a beer, he would have been here with us having a sandwich." That's not it, not for me; that doesn't occur to me. So, well, I try to say, there was a very large hemorrhage, it would not have mattered if you had paid more or less attention; the same thing would have happened. Well, this has happened; he did not realize it and has not suffered. This is very important, although the fact is terrific, but I always try that, right? And then, well, I say, "Look, I come here because I am the coordinator, ... to offer you the patient's chance, if you know his ... his will to donate. And if you do not know it, well, then you transmit your will to me, or you think about it, or try to transmit what he knew. You are the ones who know him best; how do you see it? What do you think?" And that's it, right? '

HC18

TC: You know you're going to find a broken family, a family that's having the worst time of their lives. They are in the worst situation of their lives, and you know what you are going to

find. That is to say, we are seeing situation a lot in the hospital over the history; we have addressed it. Every day and you know that you are going to see a family that is shattered. And then simply, we accompany them, talk to them but... even not talking just listening to them, let them tell you a little how they spent these days in the hospital, what their situation was, what has happened, what has not happened. Do not rush into... telling them more things. Empathize with them and talk to them for a long time. Be calm with them, relaxed, talking, let them tell you about their history, their family, their children, their situation. And then, when a better situation begins, you will find the moment because you are already advancing a little; you are taking steps, but without rushing into the request. You should not dive into the pool, and that find there is no water. You should dive into the pool and find that it is full and that the water is warm and comfortable. As good as it can be. '

HC22

'**TC:** Well, I have to explain to them first of all that... I'm very sorry for the situation they're going through, uh... offer my condolences in a way that... I think the family wants to hear the condolences, to make them understand that we have done everything possible. To give them the confidence that they were well treated in a good place, and that... What... they have behaved very well, up to par as parents, as children, and despite everything that has been tried, it was not possible. And that within all this suffering, we can help them in something, which is offering them what for us is a kind of gift, and to be able to make sense of something that does not make sense, like the death of a close relative. And maybe we can make sense of it by offering those organs to people who at that time are going through the same bad time as them. And that is more or less my initial discourse. Then it goes wrong from the first sentence you say or from the first word, but in my mind, it goes on and on, and very rarely is it as nice as I'm telling it now. But first of all, I offer my condolences, and... and I say that I am very sorry. The second thing is to say that everything that could be done was done; if this had been different, we would have been able to save his life or improve his quality of life, and they take this into account. And third, to offer them the chance to donate. '

SDC- 6

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Table SDC-6-1. Identification of ICOD candidates

<i>Estimated percentage of cases wherein identifying potential ICOD candidates was difficult</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The majority of TCT perceive that in none (5) or almost none (9) of the cases it was difficult to identify ICOD candidates; a minority (3) estimates that it was difficult in the 10-20% of cases; a relevant number (6) cannot make an estimation estimate
<i>Difficulties perceived by TCTs in identifying ICOD candidates</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Healthcare staff factors: Limited familiarity with or awareness of ICOD among professionals in other units (8); Apparent medical contraindications (5) Advanced age of the potential donor (which does not necessarily hinder organ donation) (3); Inaccurate assessment by the medical staff (2) Uncertainty regarding prognosis (3) Unknown clinical antecedents (2)

Note: TCT, transplant coordination team; ICOD, intensive care to facilitate organ donation.

Table SDC-6-2. Estimated percentage of cases in which consent was obtained upon ICOD request.

<i>Estimated percentage of cases in which consent was obtained</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 90–100% (7) 70–89% (8) 50–69% (3) <50% (1) No data/unknown (4)

